

The Effectivity Of Industrial Relations Court Services In Ternate City

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the effectivity of industrial relations court services in Ternate City, based on service process approach. This study conducted using qualitative method with descriptive analysis of interview, observation, and documentation results technique. The results showed that there are some indicators that have not been appropriate and does not support the Effectivity of the service process. The spirit of work is still very lacking, there is no reward system that stimulates the leadership to seek the creation of effective working groups as soon as the performance and development of employees, there has been no effort from individuals or organizations in achieving organizational goals and has not formed good cooperation, and conflicts that occur always solved according to the organization interests. This is very important and needs further thinking about the positive impacts of achieving organizational goals. In addition, some of the indicators that have been supported include the attention of employers to bosses, mutual trust and communication between leaders and employees are good, decentralization in decision making, vertical and horizontal relationships at the industrial relations court in Ternate City has been relatively good. Therefore, the case service process has not been effective.

Index Terms: Public services, district court, organizational goals.

1 INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country that has concept as a Law State. Therefore, principle requires all actions or deeds of the authorities have a clear legal basis or there is legality based on both written and Unwritten Law. The concept of a legal state is closely related to the legal system adopted by that country. There are three concepts of the State of Law namely *rechtsstaat*, the rule of law and the State of Pancasila Law [1,2]. Moreover, the implementation progress of Indonesian Constitution 1945 Article 24 in the application of freedom principle and independence is set forth in Law Number 48 (2009) regarding the Power of judiciary is a change of Law Number 4 (2004) is described in Article 1 point (1) stating that Judicial Power is the power of an independent state to administer the judiciary to enforce law and justice pursuant to Pancasila for the sake of legal state implementation of the Republic of Indonesia. The establishment of a special court has been regulated in Article 27 of Law Number 48 (2009) on Judicial Power established in one court environment under the Supreme Court, and one of the special courts is the Industrial Relations Court in Ternate City established under the Law No. 2 (2004). The Industrial Relations Court in Ternate City is not familiar with the appeals process as the case with the general court. In order to settlement can be done quickly, appropriately, justly, and cheaply since before the laws and regulations governing the settlement of industrial relations disputes so far have not realized the settlement quickly,

accurately, justly and cheaply wherein the law Number 22 Year 1957 about dispute settlement labor that has been used as the legal basis for the settlement of industrial relations disputes in Ternate City, can accommodate the developments that occurred in the Industrial Relations Court in globalization and reform era at the present time. Law Number 2 (2004) on industrial relations dispute settlement which is the legal base of Industrial Relations Court in Ternate with the duty and authority clerk of a court examining the file of lawsuit case that includes; dispute termination (PHK), rights disputes, disputes of Interest, and disputes between trade unions within a single company. These four disputes are not all settled up to the supreme court, because the industrial relations disputes act no. 2 (2004) has created limitations on disputes that reach the supreme court. The authority to examine industrial relations dispute dossier files as ordered by the law on industrial relations court in Ternate City which is; 1) in the first level for rights disputes; 2) the first and final level of interest disputes; 3) the first level of dispute disputes; and 4) the first and final level for disputes between trade/labor unions within a company. The industrial relations court in Ternate City whose jurisdiction covers all cities and regency in the Province of North Maluku located in Ternate, although in Article 81 of Law No. 2 (2004) affirms industrial relations disputes filed with the industrial relations court which has been established for approximately 12 years whose legal area covers the place where the worker/laborer works. Although it has been regulated in Law No. 2 (2004) for disputes over rights and termination of employment may be filed an appeal as stipulated in Article 114 which reads the procedure of appeal cassation as well as the settlement of rights disputes and disputes by the cassation judge are implemented in accordance with applicable laws and regulations, but in the judicial system is generally known there are four levels of judicial process that is; the first level; appeal; cassation; and extraordinary remedies known as the review, while the industrial relations court in Ternate City is a special court within the scope of the general justice as defined in Article 57 of Law No. 2 (2004) concerning the settlement of industrial relations disputes in Ternate which should be guided by Law No. 48 (2009) on the authority of the Judiciary.

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2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The Effectivity and Service Performance

Effectivity is a condition that contains an understanding of the occurrence of a desired effect. Therefore, if a person commits an act with a specific intention desired, then the action is said to be effective if cause or achieve the desired effect. Effectivity related to the completion of work precisely at predetermined time or can be said whether the implementation of something is achieved following the previously planned [3]. Effectivity is more emphasis on the aspect of the objectives of an organisation, so if an organisation has succeeded in achieving the goals set, then it can be said to have produced Effectivity. Thus Effectivity is primarily oriented towards the achievement of predetermined goals. Besides, service is the key to success in any business or service activities. So in providing adequate services can mean the performance of service objectives that have been established the organisation and the community was satisfied with the services obtained [4]. Public services can be interpreted as providing services with the needs of people who have an interest in the organisation following the rules and procedures that have been established. Governance is formed in essence is to serve the community. Management is not determined to help itself. Therefore it has become a duty to serve the community and create conditions that harmonise in performing excellence service to every member society in developing the ability and creativity to achieve common goals [5]. Therefore, the public bureaucracy is obliged and responsible for providing excellent and professional service. According to the concept of public service described above, that public service is an effort undertaken by a person or group of persons or agencies to provide assistance and convenience to the community or group served to achieve specific goals. Moreover, it can be said that the Effectivity of apparatus services is the achievement of an objective made by the apparatus in service following the stipulated provisions. Effectivity is more emphasis on aspects of the goals of an organisation. To measure the Effectivity of service then we can see from the optimisation of goals, systematic perspectives and employee behaviour in the organisation. Furthermore, in creating a system of government that guarantees the Effectivity of work in an organisation both government and private, the service of industrial relations court in Ternate City should generally be placed on one significant factor. This is done to support the smoothness and success of the function of filing an active industrial relations court case to attract sympathy and interest. The influence of court performance of the industrial relations court in Ternate City and the Archives of Ternate District Court if wrong place ethics and service process and the archival library are not correct then it will reduce the public interest to file a lawsuit. Labour demand is inseparable from the highly active strategy role of industrial relations court, the importance of the Effectivity of filing lawsuits increasingly vigorous from the labour and public need for the realisation of good governance. But it all depends on the willingness of every human being to change its existence from complicated handling becomes comfortable in the filing of the lawsuit case. Therefore, Performance is a work that can be achieved by a person or group of people within an organisation following the authority and responsibility of each to achieve the objectives of the organisation concerned legally, not violating the law, and according to moral and ethics [6]. Performance as the degree of achievement results of

accomplishment or in other words, performance is the level of achievement of organisational goals [6]. Meanwhile, Measurement of service performance can use several indicators [7], among others; 1) responsiveness or responsiveness is a measure of the responsiveness of providers to the expectations, desires and aspirations and demands of customers; 2) responsibility or responsibilities is a measure that shows how far the process of providing public service is done by not violating the provisions that have been set; and 3) accountability or accountability is a measure that shows how much the level of compatibility between service delivery and external rules that exist in the community and owned by stakeholders, such as values and norms that develop in society. Moreover, other indicators that can be used to measure performance, among others; 1) productivity not only measures efficiency, but also service Effectivity. Productivity is generally understood as the ratio between input and output. The concept of productivity is felt to be narrow and then tries to develop a broader measure of productivity by including how much public service has the expected results as one of the critical performance indicators. Productivity indicators are widely used to measure and know the output or output produced by an organization for a given period; 2) service quality, the issue of service quality tends to be increasingly crucial in explaining the performance of public service organizations; 3) responsiveness is the ability of the organization to recognize the needs of the community, set the agenda and priorities of services, and develop public service programs in accordance with the needs and aspirations of the city; 4) responsibilities explain whether the implementation of activities carried out in accordance with the principles of administration is correct or in accordance with the policy organization, both explicit and implicit. Therefore, responsibilities may at one time collide with the responsiveness; 5) accountability is an indication of the activities of public organisations whether they are consistent with existing regulations or policies. In this case, liability serves as a benchmark for how much the systems and operations of the public organisation are consistent with the will of the community at large. The level of consistency in the execution of activities is required to produce excellent performance [8].

Industrial Relations Court

Industrial relations is the relationship between all parties concerned or interested in the process of useful product or services in a company, stakeholders in each company consists of; employers or shareholders who are represented by day-to-day management; workers and unions; suppliers; consumer society; user entrepreneurs, and surrounding communities. In addition to these stakeholders, industrial relations actors have evolved by involving industrial relations consultants or lawyers, arbitrators, conciliators, mediators and lecturers, as well as industrial relations court judges. Industrial relations are relationships between employers, workers, and governments within an organisation, based on ethics to create and maintain the security and tranquillity of work in the company so that employers and workers can complete their tasks and functions correctly. It is also described in Act No. 13 (2003) on human resources that industrial relations are; the system of relationships formed between actors in the process of good producing and or services comprising entrepreneurs, workers/unions and government based on values of Pancasila

and Indonesian. The purpose of industrial relations is to create harmonious, dynamic, and equitable relationships among all stakeholders, to increase business productivity. While the principle of industrial relations is based on equality of interests of all success elements and continuity of the company. Thus, industrial relations contain the following principles; Employers and workers, as the Government and society in general, share the interests of corporate success and sustainability; The company is a source of income for many; Employers and workers have functional relationships and each has different functions in the division of labor or division of tasks; Employers and workers are members of the corporate family; The purpose of fostering industrial relations is to create peace of mind and work tranquility in order to improve the productivity of the company; Increased productivity of the company should be able to promote the common welfare, which is employers and workers welfare. The industrial relations court is a special court established within the district court that has the authority to examine, hear and give decisions on industrial relations disputes. Industrial relations disputes must be solved by negotiation of bipartite by deliberation to reach consensus. Furthermore, industrial relations dispute conciliation or arbitration may make the settlement. Mediation is made for the solution of interest or union disputes whereas adjudications are made for the settlement of interest disputes or disputes between trade/ labour unions.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Type of research used in this study is qualitative research with the detailed approach. Through qualitative methods, the researcher hears and sees the speakers speaking (so do not be influenced) about themselves according to their respective perspectives [9]. The qualitative approach is chosen by considering that with this methodology is expected to get the actual data and able to study deep problems to the object of research conducted, it contains understanding that hopefully will be able to get a complete picture and factual about the implementation of policy. Qualitative method is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of people written or spoken words of the observed behaviour. Furthermore, illustrative research method with the qualitative approach is a method in research status of the human group, an object, a condition, a system of thought or a class of events in the present. The purpose of this research is to make descriptions, pictures or paintings systematically, factually and accurately about the facts, properties and the relationship between the phenomena under investigation [10]. The position of the informant in qualitative research is significant. Status and role of the informant can be said as subject and also bank data which can provide primary information which is needed by the researcher about the effectivity of industrial relations court services case in Ternate City. Seeing so central position and role of informants in research, then the determination of information is done selectively. The strategy of determining the information is tailored to the various data required by the researcher by referring to their competence to be able to provide information on the focus of the problem under study. In practice, the researcher will focus on interpreted meanings based on the phrases of knowledge in depth, and not oriented to the recruitment of the quantity of information subject to research. Secondary data is data obtained and collected from textbooks, literature, journals, articles and research results. Literature Studies, by reading the documentation, legislation,

websites on the internet and documents, the concepts are drawn to provide a description of the various dimensions of the performance of welfare, knowledge, skills and attitudes and experience specific experience that supports the effectivity of industrial relations court services in Ternate City. Data collection by conducting direct observation to research location in the object intending to obtain a real picture of activities on data performance then as analysis matter of problems studied. Therefore, view used as supporting data. The interview is a question and answer process to get the data used as the basis of argument in research. Interview techniques are used as data collection techniques if conducts preliminary studies to address issues to be investigated. Documentation is a way of collecting data through written relics, mainly in the form of archives and including books on opinions, reports or Lakip, and the arguments relating to the question of the investigation. Furthermore, the data were analysed descriptively qualitative using Miles and Huberman Interactive model as follows [11]; 1) data reduction; 2) presentation of data; and 3) conclusions. The validity of data required inspection techniques. The implementation of inspection techniques is based on four criteria, as suggested by Lincoln and Guba (1985) [12]; 1) credibility; 2) transferability; 3) dependability; and 4) confirmability.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Standard of Ternate District Court Service

Based on intention to build public confidence in the judiciary, improving the quality of public services especially the justice seekers held by the Supreme Court and the judiciary bodies under it as well as possible, and to fulfill the mandate of Indonesian Law No.25 (2009) on public service, then on February 9, 2012, the chief justice of the supreme court has issued a Decree of Supreme Court. 026/KMA/SK/II /2012 on legal service standards as a basis for every work unit in all judicial bodies in providing public services. To achieve this, the Ternate District Court needs to have a quality management system, namely the standard requirements used to access the organisation's ability to meet the needs of court users with appropriate regulations. The implementation of this quality management system encompasses all management activities, resource management, critical processes for judicial administration, and other legal services in Ternate District Court. The scope of implementation of ISO 9001: 2008 Quality Management System for Ternate District Court covers all service process which is the primary task and function of all units in Ternate District Court, covering: Judicial management, case administration, trial administration, public administration, public service, Cash Management, Procurement of goods and services, Supervision, and Complaint Handling.

Industrial Relations Court Mechanism

The settlement of industrial relations disputes by the industrial relations court at the General Courts shall be made by filing a lawsuit by either party. HIR and Rbg only regulate how to file a lawsuit, while the requirements of lawsuit contents are unconstitutional. This shortcoming is addressed by Article 119 HIR/Article 143 Rbg which authorises the head of district court to provide advice and assistance to the plaintiff in filing the lawsuit. This is to avoid a less prominent or incomplete suit. The provisions concerning the lawsuit contents can be found in Article 8 No. 3 of the RV establishing the lawsuit shall

contain; the identity of the parties, the fundamentals of pretending, and the demands. The PPHI Law does not sufficiently regulate the procedures for examination in the hearing. Therefore, following the provisions of Article 57 of the PPHI Law stipulating that the procedural law applicable to the industrial relations court is the civil procedure law, except as specified in the PPHI Law. Therefore, to the matters set out in the PPHI Law, then the applicable provisions in the Act concerned, while the things that have not been regulated apply the rules in civil procedure law that is HIR and Rbg. Where there is an urgent interest of the parties and one of the parties to be inferred from the reasons of the request from the parties concerned, the parties and/or one of the parties may apply to the industrial relations court to facilitate the dispute. Within 7 (seven) working days after receipt of the application as referred to in paragraph (1), the head of the District Court shall issue a stipulation on granting or not being granted the petition. Against such determination cannot be used a remedy. The evidence is a fundamental process in the trial to know the truth of what the parties are saying in the hearing. Proof can only obtain the fact of this event. Therefore, to be able to bring a fair verdict, the judge must know and recognise events that have been proven to be true. The truth sought in public events is formal truth based on official evidence. Evidence tools in Article 164 HIR jo. 284 Rbg Jo. Article 1866 BW is; written evidence, witnesses, allegations, recognition, oath, local examination, an expert description. The decision of the industrial relations court dispute between trade/ labour unions in a company is final and permanent. Whereas the industrial relations court's decision on the district court concerning rights disputes and dispute of termination of employment (PHK) has a permanent legal force if not submitted to the Supreme Court appeals within no later than 14 (fourteen) days. One of the parties wishing to file a cassation must submit in writing through the Subordinate Courts of the industrial relations court to the local district court. Settlement of rights disputes to the Supreme Court no later than 30 (thirty) working days from the date of receipt of the request for a cassation. The panel of judges of the cassation consists of one Supreme Court Justice, and two Ad-Hoc Judges assigned to examine and decide industrial relations dispute cases to the Supreme Court prescribed by the Chief Justice of the Supreme Court.

Service Procedure of Case File

The process of filing a court file of the Industrial Relations Court at the Ternate District Court is conducted through several stages. The stages are illustrated in the case file processing flow as shown in Figure 1. From the figure, it can be explained that the filing phase of the court filing case begins with the one-stop service officer receiving the case file of the industrial relations dispute lawsuit from the parties. Further, the one-stop service officer checks the completeness of the industrial relations dispute lawsuit file filed and submitted to the court's registrar. Industrial relations to calculate the cost of the industrial relations dispute lawsuit case based on the radius scale and written in the SKUM (if the case lawsuit of the Industrial Relations Dispute is less than IDR 150,000,000, the case fee is borne by the state, and if the case charge of the industrial relations dispute over IDR 150,000,000, the cost of the lawsuit is charged to the plaintiff). At the next stage the cashier hands over the SKUM to the plaintiff and deposits the PNBK to the bank if the case charge of the industrial relations dispute over IDR 150.000.000, after

that, the officer gave the case number and recorded the data in the case registers of the industrial relations contradict lawsuit and input data to the SIPP/CTS application. Then in the next stage, the head of the industrial relations court appoints the panel of judges to hear the case. The clerk shall appoint a substitute, and subsequently, the registrar shall appoint a substitute registrar to deal with the industrial relation court case filed by the registrar of the court of industrial relations court (IRC). Further the chief judge siding day, the chief judge appointed to hand over the case file to the substitute registrar who has been selected by the substitute registrar to make the stipulation of the day of the hearing and signed by the chairman of the assembly and summon the session to the parties and then process receive the report of the substitute clerk on the stipulation of the day of the hearing and the summoning of the discussions to the parties is recorded in the register book. In the final stage of appointment of a substitute bailiff to call the parties and the bailiff makes release summon and appeal to the parties, then the bailiff shall deliver version to the registrar of the supervisor no later than 1 day before the trial begins judicial review by the panel of judges (lawsuit, answer, replik, duplicate, proof, conclusion, verdict).

Service Effectivity According to Process Approach

In analyzing the effectiveness of the services provided to the Ternate District Court in terms of court filing of industrial relations courts, the author uses the theory on measurement of effectiveness by using a process approach [13]. The indicators in the measurement as follows; 1) Attention boss to employee, superiors able to give direction and motivation to all member of group to be able to work together and work sincerely to achieve organizational goals; 2) The spirit, cooperation and loyalty of working groups. The spirit of work is the desire and sincerity of a person doing his job well and disciplined to achieve maximum productivity. Cooperation is a joint activity between two or more people to achieve the same goal. Cooperation will bring together the power of ideas that will lead to success. And work loyalty is the dedication and obedience in performing a task given by the organization; 3) Mutual trust and communication between employees with leadership, mutual trust in honesty, ability and competence among subordinates will create a situation of sharing information and collaboration and assisting in the achievement of organizational goals; 4) Decentralization in decision making, with the delegation of authority in making decisions to subordinates can improve and improve the effectiveness and productivity of an organization; 5) The existence of smooth vertical and horizontal communication within the organization; 6) The existence of the efforts of each individual and the whole organization to achieve the planned objectives, the efforts of individuals and the whole organization can be seen from the presence of creative souls owned by court employees; 7) The existence of a reward system that stimulates the leadership to seek for the creation of effective working groups and the performance and development of employees, the reward system is given as a form of appreciation to employees on the assessment of their performance; 8) Organizations and sections cooperate well and the conflicts that occur are always resolved with reference to common interests. The effectiveness of an organization can be measured through the level of conflict that occurs, when the conflict that occurs in the completion of parts of the organization work together well in

accordance with the reference of the interests of the organization. Measures of public services effectivity concerning indicators that will be described according to interviews with informants. The effectiveness measurement indicators are defined as follows.

Superiors Attention on Employees

In the organisation, the attention to employers is needed in creating an atmosphere of comfortable and conducive organizational conditions. In the case of an industrial relations court case file, the attention of the head of the general section to its subordinates is able to provide direction so as to enable all members of the group to work together and work sincerely in accordance with their respective tasks and functions to assist in achieving the goals of the organization and also in its motivation, encouraging court employees to work diligently and foster subordinates well. So that the creation of an excellent working atmosphere and harmonious. to obtain maximum results in service, the head of the general department always gives direction and motivation to his subordinates in carrying out the task of receiving and processing the file of the industrial relations dispute lawsuit case. The attention of general department head can be said to be good because when one employee has a problem, the head of the general section makes an approach to know the problem and how to solve it without harming any party. The attention of the superior to the employees in Ternate District Court, especially in the implementation of the duty to provide services on the file of industrial relations dispute lawsuit case, can be said good and also support with what is given by superiors to the employee look good.

The Spirit of Cooperation and Loyalty of Working Group

Besides, the spirit, cooperation and loyalty of working groups is also a matter of concern to measure the effectivity. The sense of work is the desire and sincerity of a person doing his job well and disciplined to achieve maximum productivity. Cooperation is a joint activity between two or more people to accomplish the same goal. The partnership will bring together the power of ideas that will lead to success. And work loyalty is devotion and obedience to the rules of the organisation in carrying out a task given by the organisation. In providing the filing of industrial relations lawsuit cases, the high morale of work and the initiative and loyalty of employees in performing the service will be reflected in the time discipline of the individual employees. The subject of time here is defined as attitudes or behaviours that demonstrate compliance with working hours which includes attendance and respect of employees on working hours and employees can perform the task in a timely and correct manner. Loyalty has been implanted into individuals in Ternate district court because they are aware of the obligations, they must meet in accordance with the rules that have been enforced in the Ternate district court, but the observation of the author of the regulatory compliance, in this case, the discipline of working hours is still decidedly less where only Monday held the morning parade, while on Tuesday-Friday there is no parade activity in the morning. Besides, from the results of the authors also found that the absence of events that appear at 07.30-08.30 in the receipt of the case file due to the lack of the applicant who visited at around that hour. The cooperation of each stage in the process of filing a case file of industrial relations dispute lawsuit can be said to be good. Based on the results of

interviews and observations that the authors do can be said indicators of spirit, cooperation, and loyalty working group in Ternate district court there are still shortages due to the discipline of employee time is always less used in the measurement of work morale and loyalty working group, but working group cooperation this matter every step in service process of case file have been able to be said right.

Mutual Belief and communication between Employee and Leader

Trust means belief in the honesty, ability, and competence of the party in performing his duties well in his position. In an organisation as well as in the Ternate District Court, the benefit of mutual trust between employees and leaders is the creation of a climate of information sharing and collaboration. When an employee believes that his ideas and information will be appreciated, his initiative and creativity will grow, the leader who trusts his employees will feel more comfortable in carrying out the tasks and responsibilities imposed on them and the communication between employees and leaders are increasingly being done. Besides, other benefits of the mutual trust are faster organisational growth, increased public confidence, the development of a climate of transparency, encouraging innovation, the realisation of alignment between systems and corporate structures, enhancing employee loyalty, and utilising all organisational resources more effectively and efficiently. The trust between the leadership with subordinates in the District Court of Ternate has been able to say okay and close, but still pay attention to the constraints that exist following the positions and duties of each. Subordinate confidence to the leadership of the Ternate District Court has been running well because every problem that occurs, the employee directly addressed the issue to the direction and has been open management where the involvement of employees in the question of problem-solving that happened. Mutual trust and communication between leaders and employees have been said to be good because in the working relationship at the Office of the District Court of Ternate does not have the distance and mutual open management resulting in excellent communication and comfortable relationship between the leadership with employees.

Decentralization in Decision Making

Devolution is the delegation of authority in making decisions and policies to managers or persons at the lower levels of an organisation. Decision-making is a process of thinking to solve a problem to get the final result to be implemented. In essence, decision-making activities background by the existence of a challenge to achieve a specific goal [14]. This decision-making aims to address or solve the problem concerned so that efforts to resolve the intended purpose can be implemented correctly and effectively. The importance of delegating authority to subordinates is crucial in creating cooperation between superiors with subordinates in solving the problems that occur. The filing of industrial relations disputes lawsuits in Ternate District Court, in its decision making, the delegation of authority to the employees as service providers who in charge of handling the problems faced by the community in filing the filing of industrial relations disputes lawsuits in Ternate district court. Decentralization in decision making in the ternate district court is good enough because there has been a delegation of authority given to

subordinates in times of emergency.

Presence of Current Vertical and Horizontal Communication in Organizations

Communication is a process because it is a series of continuous activities, which have no beginning or end and are always changing. Connection is a process of forming, delivering, receiving and processing messages. With the smooth interface, will provide an opportunity on the parts of the organization to communicate with each other and coordinate activities for organizational goals can be achieved. In relation to the file service of industrial relations dispute cases, communication is needed for the achievement of the goals to be achieved both vertically and horizontally. The vertical communication referred to in the Ternate district court in the case file of industrial relations disputes is a communication between the head of the management and the court staff, in which the leadership is able to provide direction or work instructions in the file service of the case and provide feedback on various conditions expressed by subordinates. Horizontal communication in this service is communication between court officers and PTSP employees who are assigned to the acceptance of file of industrial relations dispute cases in the Ternate district court, where court employees and employees of PTSP are able to work together as well as teamwork in providing services file of industrial relations dispute case. Vertical and horizontal communication in Ternate district court especially in industrial relations court can be said smoothly. Existence of Business from Individuals as well as Entirely Organization to Achieve the Goal that has been Planned The effort of all elements within the organization is very important in supporting the existence of an organization, the effort of each individual and the whole organization to achieve the planned goal is something that is important in supporting the existence of an organization. In the case file of industrial relations disputes, the efforts of the individual and the whole organization can be seen from the existence of the creative souls owned by the employees. Creativity owned by employees can develop ideas or determine ways to deal with problems encountered so that problems that occur will not hinder the process of running services. The absence of a business that appears either in the form of excess or creative soul that is owned in the development of services for the achievement of goals, because they are only based on existing procedures without having to violate the rules for the achievement of its own goals. The existence of a Reward System that Leads the Leader to Seek the Creation of Effective Working Groups and Employee Performance and Development The good reward system is a system capable of ensuring the satisfaction of members of the organization which in turn allows the organization to acquire, maintain and employ a number of people with positive attitudes and behaviors to work productively for the benefit of the organization. So it can be said the reward system is given as a form of appreciation to the employees of the assessment of his work performance [15]. In the filing of court cases of the Industrial Relations Court at the Ternate district court, the existence of a reward system or better known as compensation given by the leadership to an accomplished subordinate, will create cooperation among employees, job performance and discipline of employees will be increased. There has been a system of rewards which has been applied by the entire Court,

but only to the extent of the rules applicable within the scope of the Court itself. Especially in the Industrial Relations Court, no rewards have been given to employees so it can be said that the reward system has not been able to stimulate employees to seek the creation of effective performance and development performance due to the system of rewards applied by the Ternate district court there are provisions that must fulfilled in accordance with the rules that have been set, so that leaders cannot take the initiative to develop the pattern of reward system it. Organizations and sections work together equally well, and conflicts that Happen are always resolved with reference to the interests of the organization Conflict is a contradiction and non-conformity of interests, objectives, and needs in formal, social, and psychological situations to be antagonistic, ambivalent and emotional [16]. The effectivity of an organization can be measured through the level of conflict that occurs. If the level of conflict is low then the level of organizational effectiveness is also low. Conversely, if conflicts are at a high level, the organization is difficult to control, even the entire potential of the organization is used to think of conflict resolution. This will hurt the organization and fail in achieving effectiveness. In the face of conflicts or problems that occur the need for cooperation between the organization and the parts concerned. Within the scope of case file of industrial relations disputes, when there is a conflict problem that occurs, in the settlement of parts cooperating between court officials, PTSP employees who as liaison to technical institutions and communities that utilize and assess the performance of bureaucracy, in accordance with the reference of the interests of the organization. Organizational indicators and sections work well together, and conflicts that occur are always resolved with reference to the interests of the organization does not occur at all, because it can be seen the absence of cooperation between each other in response to the problems of conflict that occurred, even that happened only to blame each without any action to resolve the conflict. Therefore, the results of interviews and observations in this study to determine the effectivity of industrial relations court services in Ternate district court using the process approach can be seen comparison in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparative Result of Indicator of Process Approach in Service of Court Cases of Industrial Relations Court in Ternate District Court

Indicators	Normal Condition	Reality	Explanation
Supervisor's Attention to Employee	Leaders provide direction as well as motivation to employees in performing their duties and functions respectively.	The form of leadership support to subordinates is always provide direction-direction and motivation in running each duties and functions	Effective
Spirit, Cooperation and Loyalty Working Group	The high morale and loyalty of employees in doing the service will be reflected on time discipline of the individual employee. Obedience to working hours can create timeliness in service. Cooperation can be seen from the communication between the employees in the file service case.	Employees do not obey the hours that start at 7:30 am and the apple held at the Court's Courthouse every Monday-Friday never appears at all, even often it was found at 08.00 am the door of the court file service was still locked and there was no visible activity until 8:30 am. But the cooperation of employees in the service can be said to be good.	Ineffective
Mutual Belief and communication between Employee and Leader	Trust means belief in the honesty, ability, and competence of the party in performing his duties well in his position. Leaders who trust their employees will create a more active atmosphere of communication and a comfortable atmosphere in carrying out their duties and functions	In the working relationship in Industrial Relations Court does not have the distance and mutual open management which involves the employees in decision making, so as to create a good communication and comfortable relationship between the leadership with employees.	Effective
Decentralization in Decision Making	Decentralization is the delegation of authority in making decisions and policies to managers or people at the lower levels of an organization. The existence of decentralization enhances cooperation between leaders and subordinates in solving problems in the organization.	There has been a delegation of authority given the leadership to subordinates during an emergency situation in the case file service of a relationship dispute.	Effective
Presence of Current Vertical and Horizontal Communication in Organizations	Communication is a process of forming, delivering, receiving and processing messages. The existence of good vertical and horizontal communication within the organization provides an opportunity for the parts of the organization to communicate with each other and coordinate the activities for the organization can be achieved.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vertical communication in PN Ternate Office in file service of PHI case is communication between leader and employee, in which the leader is able to provide guidance and work instruction in case file service and give feedback to various condition expressed by subordinate - Horizontal communication is communication between court employees and PTSP employees who are assigned to PN Ternate in the PHI case file service, in which PN and PTSP employees are able to work together well as teamwork. 	Effective
Existence of Business from Individuals as well as Entirely Organization to Achieve the Goal that has been Planned	The efforts of the individual and the whole organization can be seen from the presence of creative souls owned by the employees. Creativity owned by employees can develop ideas or determine ways to deal with problems encountered so that problems that occur will not hinder the process of running services	The absence of a business that appears either in the form of excess or any creative soul possessed in the development of services for the achievement of goals, because employees are only based on existing procedures without violating the rules for the achievement of their own goals.	Ineffective
The existence of a Reward System that Stimulates Leaders to Seek the Creation of Effective Working Groups and Employee Performance and Development	Reward system is given as a form of appreciation to employees on the assessment of their performance. With the reward system will create cooperation of employees, job performance and discipline of employees will be more increased.	There has been a reward system that has been applied in the Court, but no rewards have been given to employees so it can be said that the reward system has not been able to stimulate employees to create a creative soul in him.	Ineffective
Organizations and sections work equally well, and conflicts are always resolved with reference to the organization's interests	Conflict is a conflict and interests, goals, and needs in a formal, social, and psychological conflict situation. In the settlement of sections in cooperation between court officials, PTSP employees who as liaison to technical agencies and communities that utilize and assess the performance of bureaucracy, in accordance with the reference of the interests of the organization	There are some problems that occur in the service of the PHI case files that cause conflicts, conflicting views on the problems that occur, but in the resolution of the conflict never happened at all, even that happened to blame each other on the part one and other parties.	Ineffective

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of data analysis in this study, it is shown that in general the service effectivity industrial relations court in Ternate district court has been effective but there are still some aspects that need to be improved. The indicators used to assess the effectivity as follows; spirit, cooperation and loyalty working group; existence of business from individuals as well as entirely organization to achieve the goal that has been planned; the existence of a reward system that stimulates leaders to seek the creation of effective working groups and employee performance and development; organizations and sections work equally well, and conflicts are always resolved with reference to the organization's interests.

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